

MATHEMATICAL PICTURE OF THE WORLD AS A NECESSITY FOR COMPREHENSIVE INTEGRATIVE RESEARCH OF THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Every teacher at least once in their teaching career had to answer questions such as "Where in everyday life can this theorem be used?" or "Where in everyday life can this formula be applied?" etc. The article is devoted to the problem of applied orientation in teaching university students the natural sciences using mathematics as an example.

Keywords: applied, theoretical, training, mathematics, student, practice

Introduction

The rapid development of mathematical sciences has led to a dramatic increase in knowledge about the world around us, a growing awareness of our uniqueness in nature, our mathematical and intellectual capabilities, and the development of a persistent cognitive drive.

The inventions of the 20th century and the technologies of the 21st century, made possible by advances in mathematical sciences, have transformed the face of modern civilization beyond recognition. The diversity of natural phenomena studied and the experimental methods used to study them has led to the specialization and differentiation of the sciences.

Paradoxically, this also leads to a disconnection between humans and the world around them, of which they are a part. A.A. Elizarov believes that, with a "narrowly specialized approach to the study of nature, a unified, unified view of the surrounding world is often lost, a situation exacerbated by the rapid development of various sciences, each contributing to the creation of fragments of a unified picture of the world that are isolated from one another."

In the process of understanding the world around us, people eliminate the inaccuracies of their perceptions by expanding their records of information about it, primarily through deepening their knowledge of the various aspects, properties, and attributes of objects and phenomena, and discovering new connections and dependencies. Laws are gradually revealed, principles are formed, and scientific theories about micro- and mega-worlds emerge.

Methods and materials

A characteristic of modern scientific activity is the fragmentation of science into relatively isolated disciplines. This has its positive side, as it allows for the detailed study of individual fragments of reality, but it also overlooks the connections between them, while in nature everything is interconnected and interdependent. This fragmentation of sciences is particularly problematic now, when the need for comprehensive, integrative environmental research has become clear. The teaching is unified. The science that studies all natural phenomena must also be unified. As is well known, each science operates with its own concepts. These vary in complexity, generality, and significance. However, there are fundamental concepts that occupy a special place in the system of scientific knowledge and possess a high degree of generality. These

include: "sets," "space," "motion," "interaction," "mass," "equations," "integral," and others.

Results and discussion

The subject of mathematics, as we know, includes three components: algebra, geometry, and mathematical analysis, which define the core content of this field of knowledge. The principle of continuity in modern schools ensures the continuity of mathematical education at all levels of education. Today, the introduction of integrated natural science courses into teaching at various levels of education is identified as one of the promising areas for the development of the continuous education system.

However, despite the abundance of research on this issue, a subject-based approach to teaching has dominated traditional comprehensive schools and universities for many decades. Its positive aspects include systematic and in-depth knowledge in a given subject area, the acquisition of standardized basic knowledge by most students, and so on. However, this approach leads to a fragmentation of the subjects studied, and a lack of connection between subjects in school and disciplines in university.

It can be argued that the principle of integration lies in the generalization of all known laws and principles and the establishment of those that are universal in the natural sciences. The principle of professional orientation of education is a crucial factor in the development of educational content, realized not only through the informational enrichment of educational content but also through the teacher's activities, learning motivations, and specific forms, methods, and means of instruction.

At this stage in the development of human society, a trend toward a differentiated approach to the study of mathematical sciences is evident. This has its positive side, as it allows for the detailed study of individual fragments of reality. However, it also often leads to a loss of a unified, unified view of the surrounding world, a situation exacerbated by the rapid development of various sciences, each contributing to the creation of isolated fragments of a unified picture of the world. This trend in the history of scientific development is countered by another – an integrative one, based on scientists' desire to develop a unified picture of the surrounding world. The state of science is also reflected in the system of continuous education, which includes a significant amount of mathematical knowledge, which is developed in isolation through the study of algebra, geometry, and mathematical analysis, which does not contribute to a holistic understanding of the surrounding world and the human place in it.

The integration of the mathematical sciences is driven by the need to understand a unified global process as the lawful movement of matter. A unified scientific worldview represents not the sum of science-specific notions of the world, but rather a set of contemporary data interpreted within a worldview framework about those fragments of objective reality that are the subject of cognition in specific sciences.

The growing interaction of sciences reflects the real interconnectedness of phenomena. The increasing process of knowledge integration testifies to science's ever-deeper penetration of the dialectic of objective reality, the dialectic of nature and social development. "Integration is a process of interpenetration, condensation, and unification of knowledge. A process that is objectively determined by the interpenetration of various types of material-productive and socio-political human activity, and at its deepest foundations—by the material unity of the world, universal connection, and the isomorphism of structures in qualitatively diverse objects."

Conclusion

Einstein devoted the last years of his life almost entirely to the search for a unified theory, but the time for this had not yet come: there were partial theories of gravity and electromagnetic interactions, but little was known about nuclear forces. Moreover, Einstein refused to believe in the reality of quantum mechanics, despite the enormous role he himself played in its development.

The mathematical picture of the world is part of the natural scientific picture of the world, which represents the highest level of generalization and systematization of the entire body of mathematical knowledge, which in turn is part of the general scientific picture of the world.

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